

BODY SIZE AND CLEARANCE RATES IN THE MANGROVE BIVALVE *Geloina erosa* (SOLANDER 1786): EFFECTS OF TURBIDITY DEPLETION OVER TIME

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ABSTRACT

This study examined clearance rates of the mangrove bivalve *Geloina erosa* (Solander 1786), focusing on the effects of body size (small vs. large) and exposure time (2, 4, 6 hours). Fresh *G. erosa* were purchased from Dumaguete Public Market (Philippines), acclimatized for 48 hours, and tested in aerated 5-L setups with 500 g of oven-dried mangrove silt suspended in 4 L of filtered seawater. A total of 9 individuals per size class was placed in each setup. The remaining suspended solids were measured using pre-weighed Whatman filters dried at 60-80°C, and rates were calculated as (dried residue weight - initial filter weight) / seawater volume ($\text{g L}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$). Mean rates were low: small size (0.00347 at 2 h, 0.00172 at 4 h, 0.00117 at 6 h $\text{g L}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$); large size (0.00339, 0.00167, 0.00113 $\text{g L}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$, respectively). Rates declined significantly over time in both size classes (ANOVA: $F=231-2031$, $p<0.000$), but showed no significant differences between sizes ($F=0.01$, $p=0.909$) or at specific times (t-tests, $p>0.05$). Findings support those of Argente et al. (2014), who found that *G. erosa* filtration is turbidity-dependent, with body size irrelevant in this long-lived species (Argente et al., 2014), unlike in faster-growing bivalves. Recommendations include testing at varying silt levels to test thresholds and modifying setups to mitigate low rates.

Keywords: *Geloina erosa*, mangrove bivalve, filter feeder, clearance rate, body size, turbidity

INTRODUCTION

Bivalves are proficient suspension feeders capable of modifying seston in estuarine waters (Carlson et al., 1984; Asmus et al., 1990, in Beals 2004). However, seston quantity and composition can affect bivalve feeding behavior, particle selection, and clearance rates (Bayne et al., 1989, 1993; Navarro et al., 1996, in Beals, 2004). Bivalves can sort particles by size (Stenton-Dozey & Brown, 1992; Defossez & Hawkins, 1997) and quality (Arifin & Bendell-Young, 1997; Ward et al., 1998). Bivalve species vary in their ability to sort and preferentially ingest particles (Shumway et al., 1985; Prins et al., 1991; Ward et al., 1998). Changes in food concentration can affect clearance rates and, ultimately, the growth and productivity of bivalves (Bayne et al., 1989; 1993).

G. erosa (synonym *Polymesoda erosa*), a mud clam with oval and dome-shaped shells (Sarong et al., 2015 in Nuryanto & Susanto, 2010), inhabits Indo-Pacific mangroves, including the Philippines, where it supports artisanal fisheries (Sarong et al., 2015, as cited in Nuryanto & Susanto, 2010; Morton, 1984; Germano et al., 2003; Laureta, 2008, as cited in Argente et al., 2014). Thriving in extreme adverse environmental conditions - low pH, high heavy metal concentration, high turbidity, and salinity of 7-31 ppt - it inhabits upper intertidal zones submerged only during high spring tides (Morton, 1976; Modassir, 2000; Yap & Mohd Azri, 2009; Clemente & Ingole, 2009, 2011). As a filter feeder, *G. erosa* uses gills to remove particles from the water current via a biofilter mechanism (Ruppert & Barnes, 1994), leading to benthic-pelagic mediated by biodeposition (Ruppert & Barnes, 1994; Clavier & Chauvaud, 2010).

Despite the known effects of turbidity on bivalve filtration (Rajesh et al., 2001; Argente et al., 2014), no studies have examined the clearance rates of *G. erosa* across different size classes, particularly in controlled silt suspensions. This study measures filtration rates in both small- and large-sized classes of *G. erosa* over periods of 2 to 6 hours. The results of this study provide information useful for mangrove aquaculture and sediment management.

Research Questions

1. Is there a significant difference in clearance rates between small-sized and large-sized *G. erosa*?
2. Is there a significant difference in clearance rates of small-sized *G. erosa* across different running times (2, 4, and 6 hours)?
3. Is there a significant difference in clearance rates of large-sized *G. erosa* across different running times (2, 4, and 6 hours)?
4. Is there a significant difference in clearance rates between small- and large-sized *G. erosa* at specific running times (2, 4, and 6 hours)?

METHODOLOGY

Fresh *G. erosa* of two size classes, large and small (Figs. 1 and 2), were bought from Dumaguete Public Market. At the laboratory, the clams were acclimatized and provided with aeration in the tank for 48 hours prior to the experiment.

Sediments were collected from the IEMS mangrove nursery and were sieved to separate the silt. The collected silt was then sun-dried, pounded, and oven-dried (75 °C) to constant dry weight. A total of 9,000 g of silt (500 g per container) was weighed for the 18 experimental containers, 9 for the small-sized clams and 9 for the large-sized clams.

The experimental unit setup (Fig 3-4) consisted of a 5 L bottle with a flap inside, inclined at 45°. The silt was placed in the setup with 4 L of filtered seawater, and the container was aerated from the bottom to ensure suspension of silt particles throughout the experiment. Nine replications were made for each class size.

The clearance rate was measured at 2, 4, and 6 hours, with three replications at each time point. After the experiment, the clams were removed from the experimental set-up and the seawater from the set-ups was filtered using pre-weighed Whatmann filters (Fig. 5). The filters were then dried in an oven at 60-80 °C and weighed. The remaining silt in the water was computed to calculate the clearance rate employing the formula below.

Remaining suspended solids (g/L) = $\frac{\text{weight of the dried residue and filter} - \text{initial weight of the filter}}{\text{volume of the seawater in the container}}$

Figure 1. Photograph of small-sized *G. erosa*

Figure 2. Photograph of large-sized *G. erosa*

Figure 3. Filtration set-up of small-sized *G. erosa*

Figure 4. Filtration set-up of large-sized *G. erosa*

Statistical Analysis

Clearance rates were evaluated using one-way ANOVA to test time effects (2, 4, 6 h) within each size class. Comparisons between small- and large-sized *G. erosa* at each time point were analyzed through independent t-tests for pairwise comparisons between small- and large-sized *G. erosa* at each time point. Significance was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. All analyses were conducted using SPSS.

RESULTS

Mean clearance rates of *G. erosa* were low in both size classes and time points (Table 1). Small-sized *G. erosa* showed rates of $0.00347 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (2 h), $0.00172 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (4 h), and $0.00117 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (6 h). Large-sized *G. erosa* indicated $0.00339 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (2 h), $0.00167 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (4 h), and $0.00113 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (6 h).

Clearance rates decreased significantly over time within each size class (Table 2; small: $F(2,6) = 231.49$, $p < 0.001$; large: $F(2,6) = 2031.01$, $p < 0.001$), while no significant difference was observed across size classes overall ($F(1,16) = 0.01$, $p = 0.909$).

Table 1. Mean clearance rates (g L⁻¹ h⁻¹) of *G. erosa* by size class and running time

Class Size	Running Time (hr)	Clearance Rate (g L ⁻⁴ m ⁻¹)
Small	2	0.00347
Small	4	0.00172
Small	6	0.00117
Large	2	0.00339
Large	4	0.00167
Large	6	0.00113

Table 2. ANOVA results for clearance rates

Factor	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Small-sized bet. termination	2	0.000009	0.000004	231.49	0.000
Large-sized bet. termination	2	0.000008	0.000004	2031.01	0.000
Between small and large-sized	1	0.000000	0.000000	0.01	0.909

Pairwise comparisons between sizes at each time point showed no significant differences (Table 3; all $p > 0.05$), and the clearance rates declined over time.

Table 3. T-test comparisons between size classes

<i>G. erosa</i>	Running Time (hrs)	Mean	SE	T-value	P-value
Small vs Large	2	-0.000079	0.000138	-0.57	0.600
Small vs Large	4	-0.000052	0.000025	-2.08	0.107
Small vs Large	6	-0.000040	0.000032	-1.25	0.280

DISCUSSION

The observed low clearance rates (0.00113–0.00347 g L⁻¹ h⁻¹) and significant temporal decline align with turbidity-driven filtration patterns in bivalves. The highest rates at 2 h (initial 500 g silt \approx 125 mg L⁻¹) are similar to the findings of Argente et al. (2014) for optimal filtration up to 750 mg L⁻¹, beyond which pseudofaeces production or valve closure occurs due to gill overload, as seen in *Paphia undulata*. The progressive decline indicates natural depletion of suspended solids, as particle concentration falls below stimulation thresholds documented across bivalves (Bayne et al., 1993).

The lack of size effects ($p > 0.05$) is similar to the findings of Argente et al. (2014) for *G. erosa*, contrasting with species such as *Perna viridis* having increased filtration rates with larger size (Rajesh et al., 2001) or *Paphia undulata* with reduced filtration rate with increasing body size (Del Norte-Campos & Villarta, 2010). This may suggest that *G. erosa* exhibits a r-selected strategy that differs from that of fast-growing K-selected species. Valve gape throughout incubation confirmed active filtration independent of size, suggesting physiological uniformity in gill function across maturity stages in this corbiculid.

Notably, the low rates of *G. erosa* compared to *Mytilus edulis* with $>10 \text{ L h}^{-1} \text{ ind}^{-1}$ (Riisgard et al., 1984) arise from the experimental 45° flap restricting flow, or *G. erosa*'s adaptation to naturally low seston fluxes in upper intertidal mangroves (Morton, 1984; Argente et al., 2014). These findings indicate *G. erosa*'s role in nutrient cycling rather than high-volume clearance (Grabowski et al., 2012). Future studies should test natural mangrove particle and field measurements (Argente et al., 2014; Morton, 1976) in Philippine mangroves.

Conclusions

This study shows that *G. erosa* exhibits low clearance rates ($0.00113\text{--}0.00347 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$) that are strongly influenced by turbidity depletion over time, presumably due to experimental limitations, including the constraining flap design and the use of processed silt. Body size had no significant effect ($p > 0.05$), confirming uniform gill physiology across maturity stages of this clam, unlike in faster-growing bivalves (*Perna viridis*, *Paphia undulata*).

Recommendations

1. Conduct follow-up experiments at varying silt levels (e.g., $100\text{--}1000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) to test *G. erosa* threshold limit.
2. Modify the experimental setup, particularly the 45° flap, to reduce flow restriction and potentially elevate low filtration rates observed.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study did not require institutional animal ethics committee approval or clearance, as *G. erosa* specimens were commercially purchased from Dumaguete Public Market (not wild-collected) and no vertebrate animals, humans, or endangered species were involved.

Sediments were collected from the IEMS mangrove nursery located within the institute's premises under institutional permission. No protected habitats were disturbed, and sampling followed minimal-impact principles (no rare/endangered species targeted).

REFERENCES

- Argente, F. A. T., Cesar, S. A., & Dy, D. T. (2014). High turbidity affects filtration rate and Pseudofaeces production of the mud clam (Solander 1786) (*Bivalvia*: Corbiculidae). *Biotropia* 21(2): 71 – 81.
- Arifin, Z & Bendell-Young, L. I. (1997). Cost of selective feeding by the blue mussel (*Mytilus trossulus*) as measured by respiration and ammonia excretion rates. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* (1): 259-269.
- Asmus, H., Asmus, R. M., & Reise, K. (1990). Exchange processes in an intertidal mussel bed: a Sylt-flume study in the Wadden Sea. *Ber Biol Anst Helgol* 6: 1-79.

- Bayne, B. L., Iglesias, J. I. P., Hawkins, A. J. S., Navarro, E., Heral, M., & Deslous-Paoli, J. M. (1993). Feeding behaviour of the mussel, *Mytilus edulis*: responses to variations in quantity and organic content of the seston. *J Mar Biol* 73: 813-29.
- Bayne, B. L., Hawkins, A. J. S., Navarro, E., & Iglesias, I. P. (1989). Effects of seston concentration on feeding, digestion, and growth in the mussel *Mytilus edulis*. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 55: 47-54.
- Beals, C. D. (2004). Clearance rates and particle selectivity in the hard clam, *Mercenaria mercenaria*, from warm water habitats (Master's thesis, University of Florida). <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Carla-Beals/publication/35218925>.
- Carlson, D. J., Townsen, D. W., Hilyard, A. L., & Eaton, J. F. (1984). Effect of an intertidal mudflat on plankton of the overlying water column. *Can J Fish Aquat Sci* 41:1523-28.
- Clavier, J. & Chauvaud, L. (2010). Biodeposit production by *Bractechlamys vexillum* (bivalve: Pectinidae) in a tropical lagoon. *Journal of Sea Research* 64(3):231-240.
- Clemente, S. & Ingole, B. S. (2011). Recruitment of mud clam *Polymesoda erosa* (Solander, 1876) in a mangrove habitat of Chorao Island, Goa. *Brazilian Journal of Oceanography* 59(2):153-162.
- Clemente, S. & Ingole, B. S. (2009). Gametogenic development and spawning of the mud clam, (Solander, 1876) at Chorao Island, Goa. *Mar Biol Res* 5: 109-21.
- Defosse, J. M. & Hawkins, A. J. S. (1997). Selective feeding in shellfish: size-dependent rejection of large particles within pseudofaeces from *Mytilus edulis*, *Ruditapes philippinarum* and *Tapes decussatus*. *Marine Biology*, 129 (1). 139 – 147.
- Del Norte-Campos, A. N. C. & Villarta, K. A. (2010). Use of population parameters in examining changes in the status of the short-neck clam *Born, 1778* (Mollusca, Pelecypoda: Veneridae) in coastal waters of the short-neck clam *Born, 1778* (Mollusca, Pelecypoda: Veneridae) in coastal waters of Southern Negros Occidental. *Sci Diliman* 22(1): 53-60.
- Germano, B. P., Cesar, S. A., Mazo, A. M., & Melgo, J. F. (2003). Inventory of commercially important invertebrates in Leyte and Samar. *UPV J Nat Sci* 8: 247-70.
- Grabowski, J. H., Brumbaugh, R. D., Conrad, R. F., Keeler, A. G., Opaluch, J. J., Peterson, C. H., Piehler, M. F., Powers, S. P., & Smyth, A. R. (2012). Economic valuation of ecosystem services provided by oyster reefs. *Bioscience*, 62, 900–909.
- Laureta, L. V. 2008. Quezon City (PH): The University of the Philippines Press.
- Modassir, Y. 2000. Effect of Salinity on the Toxicity of Mercury in Mangrove Clam, *Polymesoda erosa* (Lightfoot 1786). *Asian Fisheries Science* 13(4):335-341.
- Morton, B. 1984. A review of Gray 1842 (*Bivalvia*: Corbiculacea) from Indo-Pacific Mangroves. *Asian Mar Biol* 1: 77-86.
- Morton, B. 1976. The biology and functional morphology of the Southeast Asian mangrove bivalve, *Polymesoda* (*Geloina*) *erosa* (Solander, 1786) (*Bivalvia*: Corbiculidae). *Can. J. Zool.* 54: 482-500.
- Navarro, E., Iglesias, J. I. P., Perez-Camacho, A., & Labarta, U. (1996). The effect of diets of phytoplankton and suspended bottom material on feeding and absorption of raft mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lmk). *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol* 198: 175-89.

- Nuryanto, A. & Susanto, A. H. (2010) Genetic variability of *Polymesoda erosa* population in the Segara Anakan Cilacap. *Journal of Biotropia* 17:22-30.
- Prins, T. C., Smaal, A. C., & Pouwer, A. J. (1991). Selective ingestion of phytoplankton by the bivalves *Mytilus edulis* L. and *Cerastoderma edule* (L.). *Hydrobiol Bull* 25: 93-100.
- Rajesh, K. V., Mohamed, K. S., & Kripa, V. (2001). Influence of algal cell concentration, salinity and body size on the filtration and ingestion rates of cultivable Indian bivalves. *Indian J Mar Sci* 30: 87-92.
- Riisgard, H. U., Jorgensen, C. B., Korboe, T., & Mohlenberg, F. (1984). Ciliary and mucus-net filter feeding, with special reference to fluid mechanical Characteristics. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 15(3):283-292.
- Ruppert, E. E. & Barnes, R. D. (1994). *Invertebrate Zoology*, Sixth Edition. Saunders College Publishing, Harcourt Brace and Company, Orlando, Florida. Hardcover. 1100 pages.
- Sarong, M. A., Daud, A. M., Wardiah, W., Dewiyanti, I., & Muchlisin, Z. A. (2015). Gonadal histological characteristics of mud clam (*Geloina erosa*) in the estuary of Reuleung River, Aceh Besar District, Indonesia. *Aquaculture, Aquarium, Conservation & Legislation International Journal of the Bioflux Society*, 8(5): 708-713.
- Shumway, S. E., Cucci, T. L., Newell, R. C., & Yentsch, C. M. (1985). Particle selection, ingestion, and absorption in filter-feeding bivalves. *J Exp Mar Biol Ecol* 91: 77-92.
- Stenton-Dozey, J. & Brown, A. C. (1992). Clearance and retention efficiency of natural suspended particles by the rock-pool bivalve *Venerupis corrugatus* in relation to tidal availability. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 82:175-186.
- Ward, J. E., Levinton, J. S., Shumway, S. E., & Cucci, T. (1998). Particle sorting in bivalves: *In vivo* determination of the pallial organs of selection. *Mar Biol* 131: 283-92.
- Yap, C. K. & Mohd Azri, A. (2009). Gametogenic development and spawning of the mud clam, *Polymesoda erosa* (Solander, 1876) at Chorao Island, Goa. *Marine Biology Research* 5(2).